

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LINGUISTIC IMAGES AND COGNITIVE CONCEPTS

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Abstract: This article explores the relationship between linguistic images and cognitive concepts, emphasizing the role of language in shaping human perception and knowledge. Linguistic images, including visual, auditory, and metaphorical representations, serve as cognitive tools that reflect individual and cultural worldviews. The study discusses two primary cognitive approaches—logical and experimental—and highlights their significance in understanding language and cognition. Additionally, the research examines the integration of gestalt principles, prototypes, and conceptual structures in the formation of linguistic images. The findings suggest that linguistic images contribute to the organization and transmission of knowledge, shaping conceptual understanding and communicative interactions.

Keywords: Linguistic images, cognitive concepts, cognition, metaphor, prototype, gestalt, conceptualization, semantics

The image is considered as an integral part of the cognitive analysis of the lexeme. “Cognition” is related in content to the term “knowledge”. The knowledge that occurs in the process of thinking activity will have different manifestations and characteristics. This difference lies in what way and for what purpose knowledge is mastered in the initial place [Safarov, 2006: 10].

Since language is the main means of strengthening, preserving, processing and transmitting knowledge, knowledge is inextricably linked with language. According to N.N. Boldirev, from the point of view of cognitive semantics, the complete semantic characteristic of a particular linguistic phenomenon includes taking into account not only the objective characteristics of the described situation, but also the peculiarities of its perception, appropriate knowledge, purpose, choice of specific linguistic units and point of view, the presence of concentration on certain episodes [Boldirev, 2002: 18]. In this regard, two approaches are distinguished in the cognitive analysis of linguistic phenomena: logical and experimental. The logical approach is based on logical-conceptual, theoretical modeling of the relationship between language and knowledge. The experimental approach is based not on logical rules and features, but on the experience of interaction with the external world.

A linguistic image is a feeling, imagination and thoughts expressed through language. These images are formed by means of language and reflect a person's worldview, way of thinking and inner feelings. Linguistic images create harmony through the visual, audiovisual, metaphorical and symbolic properties of language.

Linguistic images can be divided into the following types:

Visual images: these images are perceived through visual perception. For example, the combinations “*red flower*” or “*black night*” can show visual images.

Hearing images: and in this image, voices and images are formed together. For example, the images described as “*the sound of the river shudder*” or “*the chirping of birds*” are examples of audiovisual images.

Metaphors and symbols: through metaphors and symbols, images with great value and meaning are created. For example, metaphors and symbols such as “*eyes flashed with surprise*” or “*youth spilled with anxiety*” fully express emotions.

In the perception of linguistic images, it is recommended to take into account not only a part of a person's cognitive experience – the logical objective properties of linguistic units that correctly represent theoretical knowledge, but also experimental properties, taking into account all types of knowledge.

A holistic image in the cognitive poetics of an figurative word is associated with the concepts of gestalt, prototype, concept, scheme, frame, script.

N.F. Alefirenko believes that gestalt is an integrative image of emotional and rational expression [Alefirenko, 2003:74]. Gestalt reflects the peculiarities of semantics of texts with rational and emotional expression. It represents an indivisible, unchanging part of worldview. Correlation of Gestalt psychology and linguistic images is important in understanding the way a person perceives and learns information. Following points indicate the relationship [Ulugova, 2023: 124]:

Integrity and imagination. Gestalt psychology takes note of the whole, which promotes the creation of unchanged images through linguistic images. Metaphors and symbols help to organize the whole, because they represent common visions, breathy details.

Form and background (Figure-Ground) and linguistic images. The form and background principle of gestalt is used in linguistic images. For example, often metaphors and symbols are perceived as the main image, while the background is used to determine the image of information.

Stratification and grouping: linguistic images, such as synonyms and antonyms, shape perceptions through interrelationship and grouping. Gestalt principles, such as proximity or duration, can be used to explain this grouping process.

Prototypes show a typical example of a certain category, while images are images or metaphors created on the basis of this example. For example, the prototype “bird” is often depicted in images with “flying” or “wings”. Thus, the prototype “bird” is expressed in a complete and understandable way through images and metaphors. While prototypes serve as a typical example for categories and images, images represent visual, metaphorical or emotional representations of these prototypes. The interdependence of these concepts helps to better understand the process by which a person perceives and initiates meaning.

Images form the imagination of concepts. The content of the concept is transformed through images into realistic and emotional images. For example, the concept of “reader” is shown in visual and imaginary form through the images of “book” and “reading”.

Concepts are fundamental in the human process of systematizing and classifying information. They assist in establishing links between specific categories and images [Xalimova, 2023: 3]. Thus, knowledge includes various methods and means of mastering the universe around us: concrete and abstract, theoretical and practical. Different cognitive structures use linguistic images to shape value-based, discursive-oriented relationships of communicants.

References

1. Алефиренко Н.Ф. Проблемы вербализации концепта. – Волгоград: Перемена, 2003. – 96 с.
2. Болдырев Н.Н. Когнитивная семантика. – Тамбов: Изд-во ТГУ им. Г.Р. Державина, 2002. – 123 с.
3. Firuza X. IMAGERY IN POETRY //Журнал: Союз Науки и Образования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 3-5.
4. Safarov Sh.S. Kognitiv tilshunoslik. – Jizzax: “Sangzor” nashriyoti, 2006. – 92 b.
5. Ulug’ova S., Abduvoseyeva N. GO’ZALLIL/BEAUTY KONSEPTINING OBRAZLI ASPEKTIDAGI QIYOSIY TAHLILI //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 124-125.